

Breaking the Nd³⁺-sensitized upconversion nanoparticles myth about the need of onion-layered structures

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Up to now, all strategies to build efficient 800-nm-light responsive upconversion nanoparticles (UCNPs) have included onion-layered structures, in which Nd³⁺ is confined within the inorganic crystal structure of at least one layer. We report here an easy room-temperature modular preparation of core-shell UCNPs consisting of NaYF₄:Yb,Er(Tm)/NaYF₄ (UC_{CS}) with Nd³⁺ anchored at the organic capping by using cucurbituril[7] (CB[7]) as an adhesive. Strikingly, excitation at 800 nm effectively triggers the upconversion emission of UC_{CS}@CB[7]@Nd nanohybrids.

Lanthanide upconversion nanoparticles (UCNPs) convert near-infrared (NIR) light to shorter wavelengths by means of multi-photon absorption assisted by real electronic excited states.¹ Their good photo(physical) stability, size-independent optical features, narrow emission lines, large anti-Stokes shift and low long-term cytotoxicity make them far superior to other traditionally used emissive nanoparticles (NPs), such as quantum and carbon dots and gold NPs.

Initially, core-shell β-NaYF₄:Yb,X/NaYF₄ (X = Er, Tm) (UC_{CS}) have been preferred due to their hexagonal crystal structure¹ together with the presence of an inert NaYF₄ inorganic shell that reduces the surface quenching effects due to energy migration to the surface.² In these UCNPs, Yb absorbs 980 nm light (absorption cross section of ~10–20 cm²)³ and transfers the energy to the activator (e.g. Er, Tm). Given that water absorbs at 980 nm, but hardly at all at 800 nm (absorption coefficient 0.48 vs. 0.02 cm⁻¹, respectively),⁴ Nd³⁺-doped UCNPs able to upconvert light of ≈800 nm to visible or NIR have been developed over the last decade with a view to minimizing water absorption and its associated heating effects, as well as

improving the penetration depth into tissues.⁵ Nd³⁺-sensitized UCL after 800 nm excitation occurs as a result of Nd→Yb→activator (Er/Tm) energy transfer (Scheme S1) due to the fact that Nd³⁺ absorption cross-section (1.2x10⁻¹⁹ cm²) is 10 times higher than that of Yb³⁺.^{5c,6}

Thus, Nd³⁺ acts as the primary sensitizer to absorb 800 nm photons, and Yb³⁺ is the bridging sensitizer, which transfers energy to the activator.^{5c,7} Unfortunately, Nd³⁺ induces a drastic quenching effect caused by efficient back energy transfer from the activator to Nd³⁺.⁸ The most widely used strategy to build efficient 800 nm-light responsive UCNPs include onion-layered structures.^{7b,9} In these structures, Nd³⁺ is confined within the inorganic crystal structure of at least one layer, it is encapsulated in the core and/or the shell in order to facilitate the energy transfer to Yb³⁺, and it is usually in a different layer from that of the activators (core and/or the shell) in order to facilitate the energy transfer to Yb³⁺. In addition, architectures in which a sandwiched shell (only doped with Yb³⁺), between a core doped with Yb³⁺ and the activator ions and an outer shell doped with Nd³⁺ (and sometimes Yb³⁺) have also been built with the same purpose. An inert and thick shell has been considered crucial to overcome concentration quenching effects in lanthanide-doped NPs.^{2c,7b,10} There is no doubt that the synthesis of these structures is elaborate, challenging and time-consuming.^{6-7,11} A new class of 800-nm-light responsive UCNPs without Nd³⁺ sensitizers is that of Er³⁺-enriched nanostructures^{2c,10,12} (e.g., NaErF₄@NaYF₄) that mitigates the concentration quenching effect.

Based on the reported low responsiveness of Nd³⁺ luminescence to surface quenching,^{7b} and with the aim of preparing Nd³⁺-sensitized UCNPs by a less challenging procedure than that of onion-layered nanostructures, we planned an alternative, modular synthesis of UCNPs with non-encapsulated Nd³⁺ ions at the NP periphery at a fixed distance from the NP surface. Here we present a new, easy to perform strategy to prepare UCNPs responsive to both 980 nm and 800 nm excitation. It consists of a modular construction based on a set of three components that place Nd³⁺ at ca. 1nm from the

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surface of a core-shell $\text{NaYF}_4:\text{Yb},\text{X}/\text{NaYF}_4$ ($\text{X} = \text{Er}, \text{Tm}$) NP. Remarkably, we demonstrate here that Nd^{3+} , even if it is not within the nanocrystal lattice, can act as a sensitizer of UCL after its excitation at 800 nm (Figure 1). This modular design is proposed in the wake of our recent discoveries, which showed not only that core $\text{NaYF}_4:\text{Yb},\text{X}$ (UC_C) NPs can be efficiently capped with rigid cucurbituril hosts ($\text{CB}[n]$, $n=5-7$)¹³ but also that the $\text{CB}[n]$ free portal (i.e. the portal not interacting with the UC_C surface) can readily bind to cations.¹⁴

Accordingly, UC_CS have been capped with cucurbituril[7] ($\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}$) and, subsequently, Nd^{3+} has been added to cap the free CB portal, thus producing $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ nanohybrids (Figure 1). This architecture would mitigate cross-relaxation processes between Nd and the activator, even when using a relatively thin inactive shell and, therefore, under the potential occurrence of ion diffusion during the epitaxial growth process.^{15,16}

Firstly, oleate-capped UCNPs, $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{OA}$ and $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Tm}@\text{OA}$, are prepared as previously described and fully characterized.^{2a,17} $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{OA}$ have an average size of $38 \pm 2 \times 66 \pm 3$ nm which includes an anisotropic shell of an inert NaYF_4 layer of ca. 3×26 nm. The size of $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Tm}@\text{OA}$ is $21 \pm 1 \times 31 \pm 2$ nm which includes a NaYF_4 layer of 4×7 nm. Secondly, naked UC_CS are obtained by acidification of $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{OA}$ with HCl.¹⁸ Then, a mixture of $\text{CB}[7]$ and naked UC_CS is stirred for 48 hours to afford water-dispersible $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}$ NPs nanohybrids.^{13a}

HRTEM images prove that the shape and size of UC_CS remain identical upon addition of $\text{CB}[7]$ (see experimental details and Figure S1-S7 in the SI). Figure 2A, 2B, 2D show a thin sheath covering $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}$ attributed to $\text{CB}[7]$ (See Figure S3 for $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Tm}@\text{CB}$). Finally, $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ nanohybrids were prepared by mixing $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}$ with an excess of NdCl_3 salt.

Indeed, the presence of Nd^{3+} in the thin organic capping is confirmed by energy dispersive X-rays spectroscopy (EDS; see Figure 2E and Table S1 in the SI).

The ratio of Nd^{3+} was ca. 2 atoms per CB molecule for both $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ and $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Tm}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ nanohybrids. This suggests the coordination of two Nd^{3+} ions at each CB free portal.¹⁹

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a $\text{NaYF}_4:\text{Yb},\text{X}/\text{NaYF}_4$ ($\text{X} = \text{Er}, \text{Tm}$) core-shell NP (UC_C) coated with $\text{CB}[7]$ and Nd^{3+} and the processes occurring after 800 nm excitation: Nd^{3+} ions anchored at the outer rigid organic capping ($\text{CB}[7]$) serve as sensitizers and transfer the energy to Yb^{3+} ions; upconversion emission occurs after subsequent energy migration from Yb^{3+} ions to $\text{Er}^{3+}/\text{Tm}^{3+}$.

High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) HAADF-HRSTEM is a very appropriate technique for the detection of single atoms.²⁰ Therefore, it was used to corroborate the presence of Nd^{3+} at the organic capping of $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$. It is worth noting that no evidence of irradiation damage in this layer was detected during the acquisition of the images. Figure 2A corresponds to an image of two nanohybrids. As it can be deduced from the HAADF-HRSTEM image (Figure 2B), these nanohybrids show a high degree of crystallinity and they are covered by an organic shell with a thickness of about 2-3 nm. The HRSTEM-HAADF micrograph shows the presence of heavy atoms embedded in this organic layer; the highlighted circle in the rectangular area depicted in the inset of Figure 2B shows two bright dots. The intensity profile extracted from the rectangular area of inset Figure 2B shows two clearly distinguishable peaks, with a full-width at half-maximum close to 2 Å, which correspond to the two bright dots. The dimensions and intensity of the 2 bright dots as compared to that of the organic sheath, allow us to assign them to Nd single atoms embedded in the covering layer of the NPs. It's worth mentioning that the different brightness of these two neighbouring atoms may be caused by their different location, in terms of height, within the layer. In fact, this aspect is related to the focus conditions and the depth of field.^{20c-20e}

The UCL spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 980$ nm) of $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}$ and $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ exhibit the Er^{3+} characteristic emission bands at ca. 550 nm ($4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow 4\text{I}_{15/2}$) with a small shoulder at 520 nm ($2\text{H}_{11/2}$, $4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow 4\text{I}_{15/2}$) and another band centred at 670 nm ($4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow 4\text{I}_{15/2}$) (see Figure 2 for $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$; spectrum of $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}$ is similar, not shown); see Figure S8 for $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Tm}@\text{CB}$ and $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Tm}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$.^{1b}

A laser scanning confocal equipment was used to determine the performance of the $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ NPs using short dwell times after NIR excitation, at both 800 nm and 980 nm. This makes it possible not only to study the occurrence of energy transfer processes in the $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ nanohybrids but it has also proved to be a useful tool to evaluate luminescence lifetime in a range of several tens of microseconds (see SI).²¹

Therefore, samples were prepared by drop-casting a water dispersion of the corresponding NPs onto a 25×75 mm microscope glass slide. Then, solvent was evaporated and the sample was covered with a 22×22 mm glass slide.

The 515-560 nm channel was used to follow the emissive behavior of $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ and, for comparative purposes, $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}$, taking into account that the emission of these NPs is the strongest in this channel (Figure 2J). As expected, confocal images of $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}@\text{Nd}$ and $\text{UC}_\text{CS,Er}@\text{CB}$ at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 980$ nm showed the green emission of the NPs (Figure 2F-G). The emission quantum yield upon 980 nm excitation of $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}[7]@\text{Nd}$ and $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}[7]$ was measured by using a Quantaaurus-QY Plus UV-NIR absolute quantum yield spectrometer (further details in ESI[†]). $\text{UC}_\text{CS}@\text{CB}[7]$ exhibited a higher emission efficiency than the Nd-capped UCNPs (1% vs. 0.6%, respectively). This is consistent with energy transfer from Yb to Nd.

Figure 2. (A) HAADF-STEM micrograph of two superposed $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ NPs partially deposited on the carbon support film; in both of them, though it is more evident in the one on top, a thin organic layer is visible; (B) High-resolution HAADF-STEM image of another $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ NP also covered by a 2–3 nm shell; in the shell, two bright dots can be seen in the highlighted rectangular area (inset at the top); these dots can be identified as Nd single atoms in the NP organic layer; (C) An intensity profile has been obtained on them. These dots can be identified as Nd single atoms embedded in this covering layer of the NPs; (D) HRTEM image and (E) EDS analysis of $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ nanohybrids; (F, G, H, I) confocal images of $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ and $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB$ at $\lambda_{ex}=980$ nm and $\lambda_{ex}=800$ nm (515–560 nm, 2 μ s/pixel); (J) emission spectrum at $\lambda_{ex}=980$ nm of a 0.3 mg·mL⁻¹ dispersion of $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ in MilliQ water; (K, L) intensity profile of $UC_{Cs}@CB@Nd$ NPs obtained from the trace of the emission showed by an aggregate after excitation at (K) 980 nm and (L) 800 nm at a dwell time of 2 μ s/pixel.

Then, the images were registered at $\lambda_{ex}=800$ nm demonstrated the occurrence of the Nd→Yb→Er energy transfer in the $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ NP (Figure 2H–I). Likewise, excitation at 785 nm of $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB$ and $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ under the same optical setup (0.497 μ m per pixel; 2.0 μ s per pixel) evidenced the Nd → Yb → Er energy transfer (Fig. S9†).

The Er emission quantum yield upon 808 nm excitation of $UC_{Cs}@CB[7]@Nd$ was 0.001%. This corroborated that the energy transfer from Nd to Yb occurred despite of the inactive shell.

To our knowledge, there are no conventional onion-layered structures to compare our nanohybrid with, *i.e.*, there are no papers reporting on the efficiency of onion-layered UCNPs with the Nd-doped shell separated from the core doped with the Yb, activator ions by the inactive NaYF₄ matrix. It is clear that there is room for increasing the efficiency of NaYF₄:Yb, Er@NaYF₄@CB@Nd by using an active shell (*e.g.*, NaYbF₄) instead of un-doped NaYF₄.

Finally, Fig. 2K and L show the intensity profiles of $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ NPs obtained from the trace of the emission exhibited by an aggregate after excitation at 980 nm and 800 nm at a dwell time of 2 μ s per pixel (Fig. S10†).

The UCL decay lifetimes of the green emission at $\lambda_{ex}=980$ nm were of 245 ± 7 μ s and 240 ± 4 μ s for $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB$ and $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$, respectively. The value was similar for the $UC_{Cs,Er}@CB@Nd$ photoluminescence decay at $\lambda_{ex}=800$ nm (227 ± 6 μ s). Fig. S11–18† illustrate the confocal images for each sample and channel.

Last but not least, these $UC_{Cs}@CB@Nd$ nanohybrids could also be used for NIR-to-NIR down conversion fluorescence imaging by following the emission of Nd at about 900, 1060, and 1340 nm.

Conclusions

In summary, we report here an easy modular strategy for preparing UCNPs comprising NaYF₄:Yb,Er (Tm)/NaYF₄/Nd in which Nd³⁺ is not located in the crystal structure of the UC_{Cs} , but

in its organic capping ligand at about 1 nm from the NP surface. Interestingly, the emission of the NP can be triggered after 800 nm excitation. To our knowledge, this is not only the first example of a lanthanide photosensitizer in the organic capping of an UCNP, but it is also the first that demonstrates that Nd³⁺ is able to photosensitize the upconversion process even when it is not encapsulated in an inorganic matrix.

This study is a proof-of-concept, but we anticipate that these architectures will open up new opportunities for constructing novel UCNPs. The easy preparation of these nanosystems will stimulate new areas of research relevant to human health.

Conflicts of interest

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. There are no conflicts to declare.

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